

histoGe Software: User's Manual

A. Aguilar-Arevalo¹, X. Bertou², Carles Canet^{5,9}, Miguel A. Cruz-Pérez⁵, A. Deisting³, A. Dias³,
J. C. D'Olivo¹, F. Favela-Pérez^{1,2}, E. A. Garcés⁴, A. González Muñoz⁴, J. O. Guerra-Pulido¹,
J. Mancera-Alejandre⁶, D. J. Marín-Lámbarri⁴, M. Martínez Montero¹, J. Monroe³,
S. Paling⁷, S. Peeters⁸, P. R. Scovell⁷, C. Türkoğlu⁸, E. Vázquez-Jáuregui⁴, J. Walding³

¹*Instituto de Ciencias Nucleares, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, CDMX, México*

²*Centro Atómico Bariloche, CNEA/CONICET/IB, Bariloche, Argentina*

³*Royal Holloway, University of London, Egham Hill, United Kingdom*

⁴*Instituto de Física, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, A. P. 20-364, México D. F. 01000, Mexico*

⁵*Centro de Ciencias de la Atmósfera. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Ciudad Universitaria, Coyoacán 04510, Ciudad de México, Mexico*

⁶*Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México*

⁷*Boulby Underground Laboratory, Boulby Mine, Saltburn-by-the-Sea, United Kingdom*

⁸*Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Sussex, Brighton, United Kingdom*

⁹*Instituto de Geofísica, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Ciudad Universitaria, Coyoacán 04510, Ciudad de México, México*

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I. INTRODUCTION

`histoGe` is a software written in Python3 used to identify γ photopeaks, rank each of them according with specific criteria, plotting spectra, subtract spectra, calculate Gilmore's statistics, rebin spectra, automatic identification of photopeaks, find parents and daughters of radioactive isotopes, among others. This program works from the command line of UNIX-like and UNIX-based operating systems or Windows operating systems, i.e., it can run in the terminal of the mainstream platforms such as Windows, Linux and Mac OS. It is scriptable and can be used to make simple routines to analyze spectra. Besides, it is capable of executing several commands in one execution avoiding multiple calls so that it can be used to make simple routines to analyze spectra. It is coded following a modular paradigm, where each module is responsible for the execution of one of the main features of the program, and are independent of any other. The modules are stored in the ' folder "modules". Those functions that are called by more than one module are stored in common libraries stored in the folder "myLibs".

This software operates using a large database that was constructed specifically for this application. It contains more than 90,000 entries of γ -lines.

`histoGe` accepts multiple ASCII-based spectrum formats such as `mca`, a standard format used by many brands of multichannel analyzers, such as the PX5-HPGe, but it also accepts `SPE` files and `Txt` files from the gammavision software. Besides, `histoGe` has its own file format with extension `hge`. The software is capable to convert spectra stored in `mca`, `SPE` and `Txt` files to `hge` files.

II. INSTALLATION

A. Prerequisites

To run `histoGe` is mandatory to have installed Python3 (> 3.6) with the next libraries: `pandas`, `numpy`, `matplotlib` and `scipy`.

B. How to install `histoGe` program

1. Installation on UNIX-like and UNIX-based systems

1. download `histoGe` files from <https://github.com/LABChico/histoGe.git>
2. `$ mkdir -p ~/.myPrograms` (Create `.myPrograms` directory)
3. `$ cd ~/.myPrograms` (Move to the `.myPrograms` directory)
4. `$ ln -s /path/to/histoGe/histoGe.py histoGe` (Create a symbolic link to `histoGe`. Note: replace with the proper path to `histoGe.py`)

- 92 5. `$ nano ~/.bashrc` (Open `.bashrc` file in nano text editor or you can use your text editor of your preference.
 93 Note: for other shells edit the appropriate resource configuration file).
- 94 6. Paste at the end of the file: `“export PATH=$PATH:~/myPrograms”`
- 95 7. Save and close `.bashrc`

96 Now you should be able to call `histoGe` program from a linux terminal. Try opening a new one and type:
 97 `$ histoGe`

98 `histoGe` can be executed in Mac OS due to it is a UNIX based operating system. So the instructions to install
 99 should be the same as Linux. Due to developers do not work in this platform, the installation was not tested.

100 2. Installation on Windows systems

101 Although `histoGe` is optimized to run in Linux, it can be run in other operating systems such as Windows or Mac
 102 OS. To install `histoGe` in Windows based operative systems follow the next steps:

- 103 1. Download Python 3 installer from the official website (www.python.org).
- 104 2. Install Python3 in your computer. Be sure that `pip` is also installed picking the option given by the installer.
- 105 3. Install modules necessary to run `histoGe` with the command: `pip install numpy pandas matplotlib scipy`.
- 106 4. To test Python 3, open a command window using the command `cmd`. Then, type `Python`. If python is correctly
 107 installed, its header should be displayed and the prompt should be active to execute any command. Type
 108 `exit()`.
- 109 5. Install git in Windows. Download it from git-scm.com.
- 110 6. Open a terminal and navigate to the folder where you want to install `histoGe`.
- 111 7. Clone the repository using the next command: `git clone https://github.com/LABChico/histoGe.git`.
- 112 8. Create a folder called “myDatabase” inside the `histoGe` folder.
- 113 9. Copy the database in “myDatabase”.
- 114 10. Run `histoGe` invoking the next command: `python \path to histoGe\histoGe.py arg1 arg2 ...`

115 C. How to install `histoGe`’s database

116 `histoGe` has functionalities to look for peak energies in a database and return a list of candidates that can generate
 117 those peaks. Also, you can search the database using the names of isotopes and energy ranges. So we strongly
 118 recommend that you install this database.

119 To install database do the next:

- 120 1. `cd /path/to/histoGe/histoGe.py`
- 121 2. `mkdir myDatabase`
- 122 3. Download the database from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437341>
- 123 4. Copy `RadioactiveIsotopes.db` to `/path/to/histoGe/myDatabase` folder.

124 D. How to update `histoGe`

125 If you have downloaded and installed `histoGe` program from GitHub using the “git clone” command, then, you can
 126 update `histoGe` function to the last version using the command “git pull”. NO NEED TO REINSTALL.

127 Future versions of `histoGe` may require an updated version of the database.

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE HISTOGE'S FUNCTIONALITIES

128

129 Table I describes the main functionalities of the program. More detailed information is available via the help option,
130 including a link to a tutorial.

131 By default, the program will search for calibration data inside the spectrum file and display the calibrated spectrum.
132 A rebinning operation is available (option `--rebin`) accepting an integer argument (N). The rebinning adds the
133 contents of N consecutive bins from left to right. If the final bin has a truncated section, in case the total number
134 of channels is not divisible by N , then the last new bin is assigned the bin content of the remaining bins. Energy
135 calibration is reasonably preserved when rebinning by assigning the corresponding energy to the center of each new
136 bin.

Options	Sub-Options	Description
<code>--isotope, -i</code>	None	Queries database to find the gamma rays emitted by an isotope.
<code>--query, -q</code>	<code>--all</code>	Queries database to find gamma rays between a range of energies.
<code>--parent, -p</code>	None	Look for the parent and children isotopes of an entry.
<code>--help, -h</code>	None	Displays help information for users.
<code>--autoPeak, -P</code>	<code>--rebin, --wof, --noPlot, --log, --noCal</code>	Locates peaks in a spectrum automatically and generates an output file.
<code>--halfSort, --halfRank, --halfRank</code>	<code>--wof, --all</code>	Performs half life ranking and sorting algorithms.
<code>--Rank, --rank, -R</code>	<code>--wof, --all</code>	Performs ranking and sorting algorithms to find the most probable isotopes in a sample.
<code>--RankAdv, --rankAdv, -RA</code>	<code>--wof, --all, --filter</code>	Performs ranking and sorting algorithms through the calculation of the Mean Square Error (MSE).
<code>--fuzzy, -z</code>	<code>--wof, --all --filter</code>	Performs fuzzy ranking.
<code>--chainRank, --ChainRank, -x</code>	<code>--wof, --all, --peak</code>	Performs ranking chain algorithm.
<code>--Rank, --rank, -R</code>	<code>--wof, --all</code>	Performs ranking and sorting algorithms to find the most probable isotopes in a sample.
<code>--stats, -c</code>	<code>--wof, --noPlot, --noCal, --log</code>	Calculates the statistics of the peaks according to [1].
<code>--sum, -s</code>	<code>--noCal, --log, --noPlot, --wof</code>	Sums two or more spectra.
<code>--sub, -r</code>	<code>--noCal, --log, --noPlot, --wof, --rebin</code>	Subtracts two spectra.
<code>--energyRanges, -e</code>	<code>--all, --wof</code>	Finds all isotopes within a range of energy.
<code>--hge, -f</code>	None	Converts <code>mca</code> , <code>SPE</code> or <code>Txt</code> to <code>hge</code> format.
<code>--eff, -e</code>	<code>--plot</code>	Adjusts the spectrum by efficiency and returns a <code>hge</code> file.
<code>--distance, -d</code>	<code>--wof, --all</code>	Performs ranking considering the deviation of isotopes from the mean.
<code>--probability, -b</code>	<code>--wof, --all</code>	Performs ranking considering the probability that a γ -line can explain peaks in a spectrum.
<code>--test, -t</code>	None	Executes a simple routine to verify that <code>histoGe</code> was installed correctly.
<code>--signal, --noise, --sn</code>	None	Calculates the background to peak ratio.
<code>--normInt, -n</code>	None	Shows the normalized intensities for a given parent isotope.
<code>--NORM</code>	<code>--235U, --238U, --232Th, --40K, --7Be</code>	Save info files for 235U, 238U, 232Th, 40K, 7Be series according with [1]

TABLE I. Some options accepted by `histoGe`. `mca`, `SPE` file and `Txt` files are formats to store spectra. `mca` file format is native of many commercially available brands of multichannel analyzers.

To make the queries for a given spectrum, an `info` file is formed containing the details of the spectrum and the energy query ranges where peaks will be searched in a simple text format.

The “`--autoPeak`” option implements a peak detection algorithm (PDA) using the Savitzky-Golay Filter [2] and, as output, it generates an `info` file with automatically generated query ranges extracted from the identified peaks. However, the PDA also can miss relevant peaks or find false positives. To increase the number of relevant peaks, a rebinning can be performed (if backgrounds are high or if there are low statistics). However, missing peaks and false peaks can still occur. To solve this inconvenience, the `info` file can be easily edited by the user, therefore false peaks can be deleted from the file and missed peaks can be included, energy ranges can also be manually edited. Section ?? shows an example of the contents of an `info` file for the case of a ^{60}Co source.

Note that allowing false peaks into the ranking process can worsen the result as isotopes that are not actually in the sample will be considered. A post-examination of the `info` file by the user is strongly recommended although ranking can be performed without it. A more reliable PDA would make the program more autonomous, however PDAs have been thoroughly investigated [3–5] and none with 100% efficiency is known, so users should always check the results from the `--autoPeak` option.

The more isotopes included during the ranking, the less accurate the results can be, and the higher the computation time required to complete the process. The `--autoPeak` ranges can be reduced using one of its suboptions (see Table I).

Some ranking procedures require more information that is provided solely by an `info` file, for example rank G needs both the `info` and the spectrum file for calculating the peak integrals and performing the ranking.

IV. HISTOGE’S OPERATION PRINCIPLE

A. Methodological approach

The general methodology for isotope identification and their corresponding γ -lines, observed as peaks in a spectrum, is described next. Figure 1 shows a flowchart of this general procedure. Before starting it is mandatory to have an `info` file that contains all the energy ranges where peaks can be located in the spectrum, Appendix VI H explains how `info` files are created. The `info` file is then read to obtain all the energy ranges where peaks were found in the spectrum. For the energy range of each peak, a query to the database is performed. As a result, a set of lists are obtained, one list per peak, and each list has the database information of all γ -lines that can be located inside the specified energy range.

FIG. 1. Flowchart of the processing done for a given `info` file. Some ranking operations may need extra information not present in the `info` file such as the gamma spectrum.

Each of those lists contains a set of γ -lines that are sorted locally (per peak) with the intention of finding the responsible γ -line(s) that produced certain peaks in the spectrum and therefore, the isotope which is contained in the measured sample. To achieve this, the sorting operation uses a numerical parameter (assigned to each γ -line) called the “rank value”, used for sorting in either ascending or descending order depending on the criterion (section IV C describes them in detail). It is important to differentiate the rank value from the position of a particular γ -line in a peak list. Within the scope of this article, they are conceptually different. Positions span from 0 to the number of the γ -lines found in the query minus one, and it should be understood that positions closer to 0 are better than larger ones. Once the rank values are calculated, each γ -line list is sorted and printed on the screen or stored in a text file. It is important to note that, although all criteria need an `info` file, not all criteria require the spectrum.

There are three classes of ranking methods considering the way the rank value is calculated. Two criteria (Sections IV C 1 and IV C 2) use the first class where the rank value is calculated per each γ -line individually without considering

176 the other γ -lines of the same isotope found for the other peaks. In other criteria (Sections IV C 3, IV C 4, IV C 5, IV C 6,
 177 IV C 7 and IV C 8) the second class is used, where the rank values are calculated using all γ -lines found in all peaks for
 178 each **isotope**. Lastly, within the third class (IV C 9 and IV C 10), the rank value takes into account all isotopes in the
 179 **decay chains**. After the rank value is calculated, there is a rank assignment operation with the following hierarchy;
 180 **(3) decay chain** \rightarrow **(2) isotope** \rightarrow **(1) γ -line**. From left to right, it can be understood as; for each decay chain
 181 each member isotope gets assigned the rank value of the decay chain, for each isotope each γ -line gets assigned the
 182 rank value of the isotope. The values in parentheses are the ranking method class, they are the starting points for
 183 rank assignment given a ranking class.

184 It is necessary to have an objective way to evaluate the performance of each criterion so that the obtained results
 185 between different criteria can be compared. For this purpose, an *ad hoc* evaluation metric is proposed. Briefly, it
 186 assigns 10 points for position zero, 9 points for position one, and so on, the sum of points is divided by the maximum
 187 number of points. The details of the evaluation metric can be consulted in Appendix IV B.

188 `histoGe`'s database [6] was constructed from the online database [7], additional data had to be computed and added
 189 to have enough information to be used with the ranking criteria (such as decay chains), see Appendix V A for details
 190 about its parsing and construction. The database entry (γ -line) with the highest energy belongs to ^{20}Na and it is
 191 located at 11258.9 keV. The total number of entries is 92453, which is 226 times larger in comparison to [8] and more
 192 than twice the theoretically used in [9]. `histoGe`'s database uses only 11 MB of hard disk space. Figure 2 shows the
 193 energies of the database entries in 1 keV bins. As it can be noticed, there is a larger amount of entries at low energies
 194 than at high energies; also, there is an apparent under representation in the vicinity of 511 keV ($\approx 50\%$). This might
 195 indicate a systematic over-subtraction of positron annihilation backgrounds in the reported measurements, yielding a
 196 slightly overdepleted energy region in the database.

197 Figure 2 obviates a problem of peak identification using a large database, that is, peaks in a spectrum could be
 198 explained by a multitude of γ -line candidates, even if the peak has a narrow width. In the next section, the ranking
 199 criteria that help to overcome this and other problems are explained in detail.

FIG. 2. Entry distribution of energies in the database using 1 keV bin width, note presence of the over depleted zone (close to 511 keV) shown more clearly at the zoomed-in insert.

B. Evaluation Metric

201 A metric to evaluate the performance of each ranking criterion is important to compare among them. The metric
 202 requires a data set where the peaks have been unambiguously identified with the corresponding γ -lines. The data
 203 set to evaluate the performance of the discussed criteria was obtained from the calibrated spectra acquired with the

204 ICN-HPGe detector using the suite of calibrated sources described in (table ??) (section ??). An info file for each
 205 spectrum was generated by the PDA and manually modified (see flowchart in figure 3). Every table presented in this
 206 paper that has a rank also includes the energy range query. The metric uses the known γ -lines energies to evaluate
 207 each criterion. It is evaluated in two steps. First, the score is calculated as follows: 10 points are assigned if the γ -line
 208 is in the zeroth position, 9 points are assigned for the first position, and so on, until the ninth position where only 1
 209 point is assigned. No points are allocated for the rest of the positions. Second, the score is divided by the maximum
 210 score, which is determined by the total number of peaks multiplied by the maximum allocated points, i. e., 10 points.
 211 The point assignment was chosen such that the criteria displayed by the true γ -lines in the top 10 results are highly
 212 favored and for the ability to distinguish between high scoring criteria.

213

C. Ranking Criteria

214 Ten criteria were designed to identify γ -lines from potential isotopes that could be present in a sample using the
 215 peaks found in its corresponding γ spectrum. They differ from other previously reported methods in how they
 216 utilize the information contained in different variables such as the emission probability (EP), the relative emission
 217 probability (REP), the ratio between the number of peaks identified in the spectrum and the number of peaks found
 218 in the database for certain isotopes, among others. The criteria have their own merit by themselves, but they can be
 219 combined to obtain better results. Before the analysis begins, the spectra must be calibrated in energy (keV), i.e.,
 220 a good calibration has to be done previously to obtain reliable results. It is important to point out that if a given
 221 γ -line of interest is not contained in the range of the energy query, it will not be used for the ranking. This is one
 222 of the reasons why it is important to have a well calibrated spectrum and to consider the energy resolution in the
 223 determination of the energy query.

224 The following ten criteria that were considered for performing the ranking and their classification are shown next
 225 for sake of clarity.

- 226 1. γ -line distance from peak mean (γ -line).
- 227 2. γ -line coincidence probability (γ -line).
- 228 3. Half-life sorting (isotope).
- 229 4. Peak Explanation Power (isotope).
- 230 5. Improved Peak Explanation Power (isotope).
- 231 6. Relative Emission Probability (isotope).
- 232 7. Relative Emission Probability with Gilmore's statistics (isotope).
- 233 8. Fuzzy logic (isotope).
- 234 9. Decay chain peak members (chain).
- 235 10. Decay chain improved (chain).

236 Occasionally, a tie among the rank values happens so criteria F, E and D were used as tie-breakers considering this
 237 order. If the tie happened with any of the tie-breakers then the other two are used using the same precedence. In
 238 case a tie remains, then I_g is also used as a tie-breaker. A description of each criterion is given next, the syntax to
 239 use them was explained in section III and examples of use for each criterion are shown in section VI.

240

1. γ -line distance from peak mean

241 This is a very intuitive method for peak identification, the rank values (assigned directly to each γ -line) are calculated
 242 as the absolute value of the difference (in keV) between the mean energy of the peak and the energy from each of
 243 the γ -lines found in the query. The means and standard deviations of the peaks are calculated through a Gaussian
 244 fit. Finally they are sorted in ascending order, under the scope of this criterion, this means that the γ -lines that are
 245 closer to the mean are more suitable to explain the peak.

246

2. γ -line coincidence probability

247 This method follows the same procedure described in IV C 1, after the distances are known, the probability (P_G)
 248 that the peak can be explained by a γ -line is calculated using the cumulative distribution function for the Gaussian
 249 distribution (CDF):

$$P_G(d, \mu = 0, \sigma) = 2\text{CDF}(-|d|, 0, \sigma) \quad (1)$$

250

251 where d is the distance between the mean value and the γ -line energy, μ is the mean of the CDF and σ is the peak's
 252 standard deviation obtained through a Gaussian fit, which is related to the resolution of the detector. The rank is
 253 assigned directly to each γ -line and it is given by equation (1). The γ -lines are then sorted in descending order, i.e.,
 254 it places those γ -lines with the highest probability at the top.

255

3. Half-life sorting

256 The rank values are directly assigned to the parent isotopes and they are simply the isotope's half-life. This rank
 257 value has time dimensions given in seconds. Each γ -line from a given isotope is assigned the same rank value as the
 258 isotope itself, the γ -lines are sorted locally (per peak) in descending order.

259

4. Peak Explanation Power

260 A single parent isotope can have multiple γ -lines which in turn appear as peaks in a spectrum. Every time a γ -line
 261 of a particular isotope is identified in the database there is an increased chance that the corresponding isotope is
 262 present in the sample and therefore, it can explain the presence of the peak. To quantify how likely it is to find an
 263 isotope in the sample, a numerical value to weight in favor of that isotope is incremented, for simplicity, a counter
 264 associated with that isotope is incremented by one. This counter is this criterion's rank value. The higher the counter,
 265 the better chance to find that isotope as the responsible for that peak because it would explain more peaks in the
 266 spectrum. The rank value is then assigned to all γ -lines that correspond to the same isotope as explained in section
 267 IV A and finally the γ -lines are sorted in descending order.

268

5. Improved Peak Explanation Power

269 The previous criterion (IV C 4) can be improved easily by taking into account the number of γ -lines found in the
 270 database within a range of interest. The ratio between the number of peaks that each isotope can explain and the
 271 total number of γ -lines found in that range of interest is the rank value for this criterion. The chosen range of interest
 272 is the energy range between the first and last relevant peaks observed in the spectrum (the 2 furthestmost in the `info`
 273 file).

274 The rank value is bounded within the semi closed interval (0,1]. As in the previous criterion, the rank value is
 275 assigned globally to the isotope, i.e., the corresponding γ -lines get their rank values per isotope, sorting is done in
 276 descending order.

277

6. Relative Emission Probability

278 The REP was calculated and included in the database for each γ -line. This had to be done since many of the entries
 279 had non-numeric EP values and the EP was not normalized in many cases. Using the REP allows to compare γ -lines
 280 among them and it make possible to associate a set of γ -lines to their respective parent isotopes knowing that REP
 281 sums 1 per isotope. More details about the REP calculation and its inclusion can be found in Appendix V A.

282 The REP weights the γ -lines for a given isotope and, thus, this criterion's rank value is calculated as the sum of
 283 the weights for each particular isotope that is present in the results of the energy queries. As in the three previous
 284 criteria, the parent isotope is being ranked, the γ -lines have the same rank value as the respective parent isotope, and
 285 they are sorted in descending order.

286 Giving high values to relevant γ -lines (large REP) from an isotope is a great improvement over the previously
 287 discussed rankings (see section ??). It is important to note that this criterion starts to use other physical properties
 288 of the isotopes, not just the energy level. Notice that as the previous criterion, this one also gives rank values in the
 289 interval (0,1).

290 7. Relative Emission Probability with Gilmore's Statistics

291 Gilmore [1] presented some statistical methods to analyze γ -ray spectra such as the total net area of a peak (A)
 292 given by $A = G - B$, where G is the peak's integral and B is the estimated background area beneath the peak.
 293 The REP and the net area can be used together to rank and sort γ -lines. For a given geometry, after correcting by
 294 efficiency as in the case of the ICN-HPGe (see Appendix ??), the net area of a peak in a spectrum is related to the
 295 γ -lines' EP and therefore also to their REP. A "modified Root Mean Square Error" ($RMSE_{Mod}$) is used for relating
 296 these values; for a given isotope, it is calculated as:

$$RMSE_{Mod} = \frac{P_T}{P_r} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\left(\frac{A_i}{A_T} \right) - \left(\frac{I_{g_i}}{I_{g_T}} \right) \right]^2}, \quad (2)$$

297 where P_r is the number of peaks explained by the isotope (see section IV C 4), P_T is the total number γ -lines within
 298 the spectrum's range, N is the total number of peaks, A_i is the net area of the i -th peak, A_T is the sum of all the net
 299 areas, I_{g_i} is the REP of the i -th peak and I_{g_T} is the sum of the REP for all lines identified for the respective isotope.
 300 Equation 2 serves as this criterion's rank value, it assigns the rank to an isotope and subsequently the γ -lines obtain
 301 their rank value as described in section (IV A). The results are sorted in ascending order.

302 The factor $\frac{P_T}{P_r}$ that modifies the $RMSE$ in equation (2), was included to penalize those isotopes that explain fewer
 303 peaks of the spectrum.

304 It is important to note that the spectrum should be corrected using the detector's efficiency considering the sample
 305 geometry. For the point-like sources with the ICN-HPGe detector, equation ?? was used. A way to improve the
 306 identification is to neglect those isotopes that have an EP so small that they cannot be measured by the detector.
 307 Throughout the manuscript, this kind of advanced filtering is denoted as "Adv". The limit used by `histoGe` to discard
 308 isotopes is when REP is smaller than 0.05. This can be modified to take into account different detectors or exposure
 309 times.
 310

311 8. Ranking With a Fuzzy Inference System

312 The criteria can be combined in order to obtain better results, in this section such a criterion is presented using
 313 fuzzy logic. Fuzzy logic [10] is a method to formalize "approximate" reasoning and it is a tool to treat uncertainty
 314 and vagueness. Unlike, classical logic where propositions can take only two values, i.e, propositions can only be true
 315 or false; propositions in fuzzy logic can have a degree of truth between 0 and 1, e.g., a proposition could be 0.8 true
 316 [11]. Based on these ideas, a fuzzy inference system (FIS) performs a deductive inference through IF-THEN rules
 317 with fuzzy sets [12]. A well known and straight forward way to implement FIS is the Mamdani's inference [13]. The
 318 steps to perform this type of inference are: fuzzification of the inputs; inference, which is divided in: calculation of
 319 the antecedents, implication and aggregation of rules; and at last, the defuzzification which converts a fuzzy output
 320 to a crisp value giving as result a number which is used as a rank value.

321 Three inputs (antecedents) and one output (consequent) were used in the FIS designed to identify and rank the
 322 isotopes. The inputs of the FIS are: $RMSE_{Mod}$ as was defined in equation (2), the peak ratio defined as $\frac{P_r}{P_T}$ and the
 323 REP (I_{g_R}); the output is a value between 0 and 1, that in the context of this manuscript will be called as "Affinity"
 324 and is intended to measure the extent to which a set of peaks belong to a particular isotope. Each input has three
 325 fuzzy sets and the output has five fuzzy sets. Fuzzy sets were defined using the well-known sigmoid and Gaussian
 326 functions whose mathematical expressions are, respectively, given by:

$$f_s(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-k_o(x-x_o)}}, \quad (3)$$

327 where k_o and x_o are the parameters of the sigmoid function, and
 328

$$f_g(s) = e^{-\frac{(x-x_o)^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad (4)$$

329 where σ and x_o are the parameters of the Gaussian function. Table II shows the fuzzy set name, the mathematical
 330 function used to represent the fuzzy sets and their parameters for inputs and output. The parameters of the fuzzy
 331 sets were established considering the designer's own knowledge about what could the linguistic variables mean by
 332 Very Low, Low, Medium, High or Very High, while also obtaining a monotonically increasing function.
 333

	Variable	Fuzzy set name	Function type	Parameters
Input	$RMSE_{Mod}$	Low	Sigmoid	(-100,0.1)
	$RMSE_{Mod}$	Medium	Gaussian	(0.08,0.2)
	$RMSE_{Mod}$	High	Sigmoid	(100,0.3)
	Peak Ratio	Low	Sigmoid	(-50,0.55)
	Peak Ratio	Medium	Gaussian	(0.125,0.7)
	Peak Ratio	High	Sigmoid	(50,0.85)
	IgR	Low	Sigmoid	(-50,0.35)
	IgR	Medium	Gaussian	(0.125,0.5)
Output	Affinity	VeryLow	Sigmoid	(-100,0.2)
	Affinity	Low	Gaussian	(0.085,0.3)
	Affinity	Medium	Gaussian	(0.085,0.5)
	Affinity	High	Gaussian	(0.085,0.7)
	Affinity	VeryHigh	Sigmoid	(100,0.8)

TABLE II. Parameters of the fuzzy sets used in the FIS. Sigmoid and Gaussian functions parameters are (k_o, x_o) and (σ, x_o) , respectively.

334 The rules used for the inference are of the form:

$$335 \text{ IF } x_1 \text{ is } RMSE_m^k \text{ and } x_2 \text{ is PeakRatio}_n^k \text{ and } x_3 \text{ is Ig}_{R_p}^k \text{ THEN } y^k \text{ is Affinity}_q^k,$$

336 where k represents the number of rules shown in table III and m, n, p and q are the indices of their respective fuzzy
 337 sets. The rules used for the inference process are shown in table III. Due to the fact that there are three fuzzy sets
 338 for each input, there are twenty seven rules with their consequents chosen from five fuzzy sets. During the design of
 339 the FIS, it was decided that five output fuzzy sets were enough to categorize the combinations of the inputs.

340 Once the fuzzy sets are defined and the rules given, the Mamdani inference is implemented so that for each isotope
 341 found in the ranges of peaks an affinity is calculated. The corresponding γ -lines get assigned the same value as their
 342 respective parent isotope, as described in section IV A. They are later sorted considering in the first place the affinity
 343 and, as a tiebreaker criterium, $RMSE_{Mod}$ was used. This criterium was chosen for its simplicity and because it is
 344 already an input of the fuzzy rank method, however, other criteria such as Ig_R could be used to untie isotopes with
 345 the same ranking value.

	$RMSE_{Low}$			$RMSE_{Medium}$			$RMSE_{High}$		
	PeakRatio _{Low}	PeakRatio _{Medium}	PeakRatio _{High}	PeakRatio _{Low}	PeakRatio _{Medium}	PeakRatio _{High}	PeakRatio _{Low}	PeakRatio _{Medium}	PeakRatio _{High}
REP _{Low}	ML	MM	MM	MVL	ML	ML	MVL	MVL	MVL
REP _{Medium}	MM	MH	MH	MM	MM	MH	ML	MM	MH
REP _{High}	MVH	MVH	MVH	MH	MH	MVH	MH	MH	MH

TABLE III. FIS rules used in **histoGe**'s fuzzy rank. MVL, ML, MM, MH and MVH refer to the affinity output fuzzy sets: Very Low, Low, Medium, High and Very High, respectively.

346 9. Chain using Peak Explanation criterion

347 In some spectra, the presence of some peaks can be due to γ -lines from several isotopes that are connected to each
 348 other via a decay chain. This motivates to design criteria that rank chains instead of ranking isotopes alone. As
 349 explained in Appendix V A, **histoGe**'s database includes already decay chain information.

350 This criterion consists first in identifying the participating isotopes (in the same way as the previous ranking
 351 criteria), then the participating chains are selected if there is at least one isotope chain member from the previous
 352 operation. For each chain the “Improved Peak Explanation Power” criterion (section IV C 4) is performed for each of
 353 the isotopes present in the chain. The chain’s rank value is obtained by averaging the respective isotope rank values
 354 with respect to the number of isotopes belonging to the chain. Then, as explained in section IV A, the resulting rank
 355 is then assigned to the member isotopes and then from the isotopes to the respective γ -lines. Lastly, γ -lines are sorted
 356 in descending order for each of the peaks of the spectrum.

357 10. Chain using Relative Emission Probability

358 This method is very similar to the one described in section IV C 9 applied to a chain. The REP for each isotope
 359 belonging to a chain is summed (as in section IV C 6) using the identified γ -lines and then the result is averaged
 360 considering all isotopes of the chain. As described in section IV A, γ -line rank value assignment goes from chain to
 361 isotope chain members and then from each isotope to the corresponding γ -lines. Sort is done in descending order.

362 V. THE LOCAL DATABASE

363 A. Construction of the database

364 A local database is used by the application in contrast to the remote versions that are publicly available in the web
 365 such as [7, 14, 15]. Remote querying impacts negatively the performance of the implementation since the availability
 366 of a database could be limited during specific times or places, the number of queries made by the client could also be
 367 limited, or the server might impose a limit to the number of results per query, which is a common practice placed in
 368 many public databases. This imposes serious constraints when performing the ranking operations, in addition, any
 369 lag in the network could severely affect the computation time needed to obtain a result.

370 The information used by the application was downloaded from the widely known WWW Table of Radioactive
 371 Isotopes (TRI) [7]. The parsing of the online database was performed by making queries in defined energy ranges
 372 to guarantee that all available γ -lines in the TRI were considered since the website has a restriction to display a
 373 maximum number of results per query. The parsed information was stored in a SQLite3 file. A small fraction of
 374 repeated entries was manually removed. This took place when there was a γ -line matching the final and end points
 375 of two consecutive energy intervals. For each γ -line the TRI [7] contains the following information:

- 376 • The photon energy and its uncertainty (in keV).
- 377 • An emission probability (EP) and its uncertainty.
- 378 • A decay mode.
- 379 • A half-life and its uncertainty.
- 380 • A parent isotope.

381 This information is not sufficient to implement all the ranking criteria (section III), so further data was added to
 382 the SQLite3 file. The information added to the database was an extra entry for the positron electron annihilation,
 383 as well as the alpha decay channels. In addition, decay chains of some isotopes were generated using the information
 384 of the alpha decays and stored in the database using a string format. There were some modifications to the original
 385 information from the TRI database, since some entries were empty or contained non-numerical characters which were
 386 incompatible with the calculations performed by the application, besides, there were entries where the EP was below
 387 or above 1 (100%). A program was written to replace these entries with a Relative Emission Probability (REP). The
 388 REP was adopted since it facilitates the implementation of the ranking criteria discussed in this paper.

389 Some modifications were included before the REP was calculated. First, half of the lowest value for the EP of an
 390 isotope was added to all empty entries for that isotope. This considers that if an EP is not reported, it means that
 391 it is not relevant and a relatively small value is assigned arbitrarily. Second, for non-numerical EP entries, 1%
 392 was assigned to all those entries to have an EP value with the same weight. Next, a total EP was calculated by adding
 393 the individual EP values for that isotope and finally, the EP values for that isotope were replaced by the total EP
 394 divided by its original EP. These assumptions guarantee that every entry in the local database has a numerical REP
 395 for each γ -line. These modifications to the local database considerably facilitate the implementation of all ranking

criteria, as well as eases operations such as comparisons between two different peak integrals in a spectrum. The local database with all the modifications and additions described is available to download from [6].

The TRI database includes entries for X-rays but their information is incomplete unlike the information for γ -rays. A similar local database can be built following the same procedure described here, but it is beyond the scope of this work since our experimental application is oriented to γ -ray spectroscopy with HPGe detectors.

B. Querying the database

The query of an energy to the local database is the basic operation for the ranking algorithms. They select database entries with γ -lines between a minimum and a maximum value of energy, and arrange them in a list which contains some properties such as parent isotope, level energy, etc. (described in Appendix V A).

In the context of the `histoGe` software, a peak is not considered as a single point in a spectrum describing a local maximum but as a region of points whose counts are distributed along the energy axis, they are proportional to the event rate, and they are higher than those of the points in their immediate vicinity. The region of interest (ROI) of a peak is formed by the corresponding channels, whose number is proportional to the energy, of those points in the peak. This includes the local maximum that would be typically considered because it is inside of the ROI. The channels for each peak define an energy query range where the minimum and maximum values are the lower and upper bounds for each query to the database. Appendix III describes briefly the implementation of the peak detection algorithm (PDA) used to automatically set the range of a peak. It is always recommended to perform a visual inspection on the spectra.

Clearly, as the measured spectra will be affected by the finite energy resolution of the detector, the range of energies underneath a given peak may contain many possible γ -lines.

For every peak identified in the spectrum, an energy query is performed whose initial and final values cover completely the ROI of its respective peak, e.g., figure ?? shows in red the ROI for each of the chosen peaks in the ^{133}Ba spectrum. Each query returns a list of entries that are sorted from lower to higher energy. It is very unlikely that the energy peaks identified will correspond to energy values at the edges of the energy range, since the query is performed in an interval where the peak is located close to its center. Database energy queries are done using a specific ASCII file named `info` file, which can be generated by `histoGe` using an automated algorithm or generated manually. An `info` file is just a simple summary file to do an analysis of the spectrum where the peaks can be identified without considering their number of events. For a given spectrum, the `info` file permits to perform a set of database queries (multi-query). Figure 6 shows a flowchart describing the process when using an `info` file. An `info` file contains a reduced set of information from a spectrum, which is:

- The energy range of the spectrum, in keV.
- A unique index (tag) for each peak identified in the spectrum. If the PDA is executed, the tag is a number in ascending order from left to right.
- An energy range where the query will be performed for each tag in keV

The following is an example of the contents of the `info` file used for the ^{60}Co spectrum (section ??, figure ??):

```
#SPECTRUMRANGE: 0.6764,1650
      start      end
Co60_1  1160.84  1182.18
Co60_2  1323.41  1340.54
```

After querying the database using the “-q” option of `histoGe`, as described in Appendix III, 751 and 500 entries were identified for the two lines from the ^{60}Co decay, which have an approximate width of 22 keV and 17 keV, respectively. These numbers of entries are consistent with the integral of those energy ranges in the full database, considering 1 keV bins. The number of results in both queries is higher than the entire database of [8], which is a challenge for the proposed criteria (section III). Tags do not play a role in any part of the ranking process, they only serve as unique identifiers to reference the peaks in question. The tags are displayed near the maximum of each peak when the histogram is plotted, as can be seen in figures ?? and ?. The `info` file also serves as a simple contextualization tool in the sense that a particular set of queries will belong to a particular spectrum, and therefore the presence of a specific parent isotope could be inferred. This aspect is exploited by the proposed criteria through a rank value. An `info` file can also be used to perform operations in the spectrum such as integration over the energy range for each peak. A parameter related to the detector’s energy resolution such as the FWHM can be used to define these energy ranges. The main methods described here do not require a particular energy resolution and they could

FIG. 3. Flowchart for creating an `info` file and doing the multi queries. The dotted broken block refers to optional manual adjustments that the spectroscopist could be done to the `info` file before any query to the database is done.

447 be applied to detectors with worse energy resolution in comparison to HPGe, such as NaI, however, the number of
 448 possible γ -lines that are candidates to identify the peak will increase.

449 VI. TUTORIAL

450 A. Where to download the spectra for this tutorial

451 To download the spectra files go to this link:

452 https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1uGGMeDbW5A1VkVmWUWYcfrChn6fBE_Lb?usp=sharing

453 Once that the files are in a local folder

454 B. How to get help

455 To get help you can simply execute it with no arguments:

456 `$ histoGe`

457 -----
 458 `histoGe's SYNTAX`
 459 -----

```

461 usage: histoGe (-h|--help) #for extended help
462 histoGe file1.ext [file2.ext ...] #Multifile plot or query database depending of ext
463 histoGe (-q|--query) iEner fEner #Gammas in range iEner to fEner
464 histoGe (-i|--isotope) Isotope1 Isotope2 ... #Gammas of Isotopes
465 histoGe (-p|--parent) Isotope1 Isotope2 ... #Parent and childs isotopes
466 histoGe (-r|--sub) file1.ext file2.ext #Substraction of file1 minus file2
467 histoGe (-s|--sum) file1.ext file2.ext ... #Addition of all files
468 histoGe (-t|--test) #Runs a test to probe histoGe
469 histoGe (-P|--autoPeak) file1.ext #Find automatically the peaks of spectrum
470 histoGe (-e|--energyRanges) file1.info #Consult all the isotopes found for each peak
471 histoGe (-c|--stats) file1.info file2.ext #Calculates Gilmore statistics for each peak
472 histoGe (-f|--hge) file2.ext #Converts the SPE, Txt or mca files to hge format
473 histoGe (-n,--normInt) Isotope1 Isotope2 ... #isplays relative emission probability from database
474 histoGe (-R|--Rank|--rank) file1.info #Performs ranking to find most probable isotope
475 histoGe (--halfSort|--halfRank|--halfRank) file1.info #Performs ranking using half-life
476 histoGe (--RA|--RankAdv|--rankAdv) File1.info File1.ext #Performs ranking using total net area
477 and the relative emission probability
478 histoGe (--fuzzy|--fuzzyRank|--fuzzyrank|-z) File1.info File1.ext #Performs ranking using fuzzy
479 logic
480 histoGe (--chainRank|--ChainRank|-x) File1.info #Performs ranking using decay chains
481 histoGe (--distance|-d) File1.info File1.ext #Performs ranking calculating the deviation between
482 the mean value of peaks and the energy of the -lines
483 histoGe (--distance|-d) File1.info File1.ext #Performs ranking using -line calculating the
484 cumulative distribution function
  
```

485 Valid extensions are:

```

486     .Txt
487     .SPE
488     .spe
489     .mca
490     .info
  
```

491 However the canonical way to get help is via de -h option:

492 \$ histoGe -h

493

494

495 -----
 495 EXTENDED HELP OF histoGe
 496 -----

496

497

498 MAIN OPTIONS

499

500 If no main option are provided then histoGe performs a query to
 501 database if extension of the file is .info, in other case, performs
 502 a multiplot with the files provided,e.g.:

503

504 histoGe file1.extension [file2.extension ...]

505

506 The histoGe's main option are:

507

508 -q|--query: Query the database to find isotopes that
 509 radiate gammas in the range from initial energy
 510 (iEner) to final energy (fEner) both in KeV, e.g.:
 511 histoGe -q 100 101

512

513 -i|--isotope: Query the database to find gammas of each
 514 isotopes, e.g.:
 515 histoGe -i 60Co 241Am

516

517 -p|--parent: Query the database looking for the parent
 518 isotope and the child or children isotopes, e.g.:
 519 histoGe -p 60Co 241Am

520

521 -r|--sub: Substraction of two sprectra, i.e., File2 is
 522 substracted to File1.ext, e.g.:
 523 histoGe -r File1.ext File2.ext

524

525 --rebin: Channels of the spectrum are rebined, it is just
 526 need necessary to specify how many channels do you
 527 want to rebin. In any case if the rebin number is
 528 not specified the default rebin number is 5. e.g.:
 529 histoGe File.ext --rebin 6

530

531 -s|--sum: Sumation of spectra. The option can sum all the
 532 spectra that the user need, e.g.:
 533 histoGe -s File1.ext File2.ext

534

535 -t|--test: Performs a test. If histoGe was installed
 536 successfully, then, test actions are executed
 537 without errors, e.g.:
 538 histoGe -t

539

540 -P|--autoPeak: Look for peaks in a spectrum and generates
 541 a .info file which includes the ranges of the peaks
 542 found. It works better if the spectrum is rebinned,
 543 e.g.:
 544 histoGe --autoPeak File1.ext

545

546 -e|--energyRanges: Look for all the isotopes that are in the
 547 ranges specified for each peak in the .info file,
 548 e.g.:
 549 histoGe -e File1.info

550

551 -c|--stats: Calculate the Gilmore's statistics for each peak
 552 in the .info file, e.g.:
 553 histoGe -c File1.info File1.ext *

```

554
555 -f|--hge: Converts the SPE, Txt or mca files to hge format.
556         histoGe -f File1.ext
557
558 -n,--normInt: Displays relative emission probability from
559         database.
560         histoGe -n 60Co 241Am
561
562 -R|--Rank|--rank: Performs a ranking for each peak contained
563         in the .info file in order to find the most probable
564         isotopes that explain the peaks observed in the
565         spectrum, e.g:
566         histoGe -R File1.info
567
568 --halfSort|--halfRank|--halfrank: Performs ranking using the
569         half-life of the isotopes.
570         histoGe --halfSort File1.info
571
572 --RA|--RankAdv|--rankAdv: Performs ranking using total net area
573         and the relative emission probability.
574         histoGe File1.info File1.ext *
575
576 --fuzzy|--fuzzyRank|--fuzzyrank|-z: Performs ranking using fuzzy
577         logic. It needs to run an .info and valid spectrum, e.g.:
578         histoGe -z File1.info File1.ext *
579
580 --chainRank|--ChainRank|-x': Performs ranking using decay
581         chains.
582         histoGe -x File1.info
583
584 --distance|-d: Performs ranking calculating the deviation between
585         the mean value of peaks and the energy of the -lines.
586         histoGe -b File1.info File1.ext *
587
588 --probability|-b: Performs ranking using -line calculating
589         the cumulative distribution function for the Gaussian
590         distribution. It needs an .info file and valid spectrum, e.g.:
591         histoGe -b File1.info File1.ext *
592
593 --sources: Creates an .info file for naturally occurring radioactive
594         materials (NORM) according with table 16.1 of Practical Gamma-ray
595         spectrometry of Gordon Gilmore.

```

596 *This option needs and .info file and the spectrum.

597 SUBOPTIONS OF MAIN OPTIONS

```

600         OPTIONS          SUBOPTIONS
601
602         -h|--help        None
603
604         -q|--query:      --all: Shows all the results found in a
605                         query.
606
607         -i|--isotope:    None
608
609         -p|--parent:      None
610
611         -r|--sub:        --noCal: Indicates that the file is not
612                         calibrated.
613
614
615                         --log: Logarithmic scale in plot.
616
617                         --noPlot: No plot of the subtraction.

```

```

618
619         --wof: Write output file with result.
620
621         --rebin: Channels are rebined.
622
623     -s|--sum:         --noCal: Indicates that the file is not
624                       calibrated.
625
626                       --log: Logarithmic scale in plot.
627
628                       --noPlot: No plot of the subtraction.
629
630                       --wof: Write output file with result.
631
632     -t|--test:       None
633
634     -P|--autoPeak:   --rebin: Channels are rebined.
635
636                       --wof: Write output file with result.
637
638                       --noPlot: No plot of the subtraction.
639
640                       --log: Logarithmic scale in plot.
641
642                       --noCal: Indicates that the file is not
643                       calibrated.
644
645     -e|--energyRanges: --all: Shows all the results found in a
646                       query.
647
648                       --wof: Write output file with result.
649
650     -c|--stats:      --wof: Write output file with result.
651
652                       --noPlot: No plot of the subtraction.
653
654                       --noCal: Indicates that the file is not
655                       calibrated.
656
657                       --log: Logarithmic scale in plot.
658
659                       --rebin: Channels are rebined.
660
661     -f|--hge: None
662
663     -n,--normInt: None
664
665     -R|--Rank|--rank: --wof: Write output file with result.
666
667                       C|D|E: These options allow the user to choose
668                               a rank to sort the output isotope list giving
669                               priority. The output table will display three
670                               columns of different rankings and they will be
671                               ordered according to the rank that has been
672                               chosen between options C, D or E. In case no
673                               option has been selected, the default ordering
674                               used in the case that it does not be indicated
675                               is rank E.
676
677                               --all: Shows all the results found in a
678                               query.
679
680     --halfSort|--halfRank|--halfrank: --all: Displays all
681     isotopes in the list.

```

```

682
683         --wof: Write output file with result.
684
685 --RA|--RankAdv|--rankAdv: --wof: Write output
686         file with result.
687
688         --all: displays all isotopes in the list.
689
690         --filter: removes those isotopes with relative
691         emission probability smaller than 0.05.
692
693 --fuzzy|--fuzzyRank|--fuzzyrank|-z: --wof: Write output
694         file with result.
695
696         --all: displays all isotopes in the list.
697
698         --filter: removes those isotopes with relative
699         emission probability smaller than 0.05.
700
701
702 --chainRank|--ChainRank|-x: --wof: Write output
703         file with result.
704
705         --all: displays all isotopes in the list.
706
707         --peak: uses relative emission probability to
708         make ranking.
709
710 --distance|-d: --all: Shows all the results found in a
711         query.
712
713         --wof: Write output file with result.
714
715 --probability|-b: --all: Shows all the results found in a
716         query.
717
718         --wof: Write output file with result.
719
720 --NORM:    --235U: Returns and .info file for 235U serie.
721
722             --238U: Returns and .info file for 238U serie.
723
724             --232Th: Returns and .info file for 232Th serie.
725
726             --40K: Returns and .info file for 40K serie.
727
728             --7Be: Returns and .info file for 7Be serie.
729

```

RANKING RESULT DISPLAY

```

730
731
732 When a ranking method is chosen, a dataframe is displayed and
733 its ordering shows its best results. Notice that the columns
734 are labeled with letters from A to J, this labels refer to
735 a rank method described in the manuscript titled "Contextual
736 isotope ranking criteria for peak identification in gamma
737 spectroscopy using a large database", and the rank method
738 corresponding to each label will be show as follows.
739

```

```

740     Label: Ranking method
741

```

```

742     A:      Gamma-line distance from mean
743     B:      Gamma-line coincidence probability
744     C:      Half-life sorting
745     D:      Peak Explanation Power

```

746 E: Improved Peak Explanation Power
 747 F: Relative Emission Probability
 748 G: Relative Emission Probability with Gilmore's Statistics
 749 H: Ranking With a Fuzzy Inference System
 750 I: Chain using Peak Explanation criterion
 751 J: Chain using Relative Emission Probability

752
 753 The manuscript is in preparation now, once it is published,
 754 please look for it using the title.
 755

756 VALID FILES

757
 758 Valid extensions are: .Txt, .SPA, .mca and .info

759
 760 .Txt files: Format file of gammavision software.

761
 762 .SPA files: Format file developed and used in Boulby
 763 Laboratory.

764
 765 .mca files: File format of micro-mca or px5 hardware.

766
 767 .info files: File used to store the ranges of peaks. Usually,
 768 is generated with --autoPeak main option.

770 DOWNLOADABLE FILES

771
 772 A tutorial file can be consulted in:

773
 774 <https://bit.ly/2QL8FYj>

775
 776 Some .mca files to try histoGe can be downloaded from:

777
 778 <https://bit.ly/2WNS36h>

779
 780 Database can be downloaded from:

781
 782 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437341>

784 EXECUTION OF MULTIPLE COMMANDS

785
 786 histoGe can execute several commands in a single run.
 787 Commands must be separated by "!" character, for example:

788
 789 `histoGe Command_1 ! Command_2 ! ... ! Command_N`

794 C. How to plot a spectrum

795 To plot a spectrum, execute "\$ histoGe filename.xxx" .

796 For example:

797 \$ histoGe am241.mca

798 Note: Spectra can be found at <https://bit.ly/2WNS36h>

799 D. How to plot multiple spectra

800 histoGe can plot as many files as desired. Execute: "\$ histoGe namefile1.xxx namefile2.xxx ...namefileN.xxx".

801 \$ histoGe am241-bkgd_070kev.mca am241.mca bkgd_0-70kev.mca

FIG. 4. An americium 241 spectrum.

FIG. 5. Multi spectrum plot, this example shows a subtracted background from am241 spectrum, the background and the am241 source spectrum.

802

E. How to rebin a spectrum

803 `$ histoGe am241.mca --rebin 11`

FIG. 6. A rebinned americium 241 spectrum, bottom plot is displayed with a Y log scale

804

F. How to plot using logarithmic scale

805 `histoGe` is capable of plotting in sign logarithmic scale in the Y axis.

806 It is possible to combine extra options, e. g.:

807 `$ histoGe am241.mca --autoPeak --log --rebin 30`

808 `$ histoGe am241.mca --autoPeak --log --rebin 20 --noCal`

809

G. How to use autoPeak extra option

810 `histoGe` program can mark peaks found. Execute:

811 `"$ histoGe filename.xxx --autoPeak"`.

812 `$ histoGe am241.mca --autoPeak --log --rebin 11`

FIG. 7. Two rebinnings of the same americium 241 calibrated (top) and not calibrated (bottom) displayed with channels

813

H. How to make an info file

814 The `info` file is a text file generated automatically when `-autoPeak` and `-wof` options are used together or the user
 815 can make its own `x` file. In the file are located a list of energy ranges and it is used to indicate to `histoGe` program
 816 where the peaks of interest are located. The structure of the file is:

```
817 # Information about .info file
818 # Comments
819 # Any other relevant information
820 # Note that lines that begin with # are ignored
821 #SPECRANGE: energy_min, energy_max
822 tag_name_1 Energy_Min Energy_Max
823 tag_name_2 Energy_Min Energy_Max
824 tag_name_3 Energy_Min Energy_Max
```

825
 826 You can add as much lines as needed. For example, `am241.info` is:

```
827
828 #-----
829 #This is the info file to calculate statistics of some peaks of
```


FIG. 8. An americium 241 plot with regions of interest marked and peaks labeled.

```

830 #am241.mca file.
831 #-----
832 am241_P1 16 18.5
833 am241_P2 25.5 27
834 am241Main 58 61
835
836 note:
837 #SPECRANGE line may not be in the file but it helps in some analysis

```

I. How to plot spectra and fit peaks using and info file

839 To make a plot and fit using the infofile execute: “\$ histoGe filename.xxx -c file.info”.

840 For example:

```
841 $ histoGe am241.mca -c am241.info
```

842 Also, the histoGe program gives extra information, i.e., the next information is printed in the terminal:

	Tags	NetArea	Area+ExtBkgd	GrossInt	Background	Sigma A
843	am241 P1	76830.0	76125.0	87687.0	10857.0	313.917187
	am241 P2	60046.5	60046.5	62154.0	2107.5	253.498521
	am241 P3	1946814.0	1948419.5	1984163.0	37349.0	1421.798861

J. How use Gilmore statistics

845 histoGe with the option -c is capable to calculate some statistical parameters reported in “Practical Gamma-Ray Spectrometry” by Gordon R. Gilmore. The implemented extra options are:

847 --netArea: Calculates net area under the peak. --grossInt: Calculates gross integral of the peak. --extBkIn: Calculates of the peak taking into account surrounding bins (5 by default) before and after the region of interest.

849 --gSigma: Calculates Sigma using Gilmore’s method. --extSigma: Same as gSigma but using 5 bins before and after region.

851 To use this extraoptions, execute:

852 “\$ histoGe filename.xxx -c filename.info --ExtraOptions”. For

853 example:

```
854 $ histoGe am241.mca -c am241.info --netArea
```

```
855 #tags netArea
```

```
856 am241_P1 26347.00
```

```

857 am241_P2 55489.00
858 am241Main 1946924.50
859 $ histoGe am241.mca -c am241.info --grossInt
860 #tags grInt
861 am241_P1 61963.00
862 am241_P2 60529.00
863 am241Main 1984163.00
864 $ histoGe am241.mca -c am241.info --gSigma
865 #tags gSigma
866 am241_P1 312.38
867 am241_P2 256.06
868 am241Main 1421.76
869 $ histoGe am241.mca -c am241.info --extSigma
870 #tags extSigma
871 am241_P1 678.87
872 am241_P2 381.05
873 am241Main 1799.75

```

874 K. How to combine extra options

875 Note that the histoGe program with “-c” option is capable to manage more than 1 extra option. For example, ex-
876 ecute: “\$ histoGe filename.xxx -c filename.info --ExtraOption1 --ExtraOption2 ... --ExtraOptionN”
877 \$ histoGe am241.mca -c am241.info --extSigma --grossInt
878 #tags grInt extSigma
879 am241_P1 61963.00 678.87
880 am241_P2 60529.00 381.05
881 am241Main 1984163.00 1799.75

882 L. How to query the database using an isotope’s name

```

883 The syntax is : $ histoGe -i isotope’s_name
884 $ histoGe -i 241Am

885 The isotope consulted is 241Am
886 Eg (keV)  Ig (%)  Decay mode  Half life  Parent
887 13.81 2      a    432.2 y 7    241Am
888 26.3448 2    2.40 2    a    432.2 y 7    241Am
889 27.03      a    432.2 y 7    241Am
890 31.4       a    432.2 y 7    241Am
891 32.183    0.0174 4    a    432.2 y 7    241Am
892 33.1964 3    0.126 3    a    432.2 y 7    241Am
893 38.54 3      a    432.2 y 7    241Am
894 42.73 5     0.0055 11   a    432.2 y 7    241Am
895 43.423 10    0.073 8    a    432.2 y 7    241Am
896
897 *This list was truncated

```

898 M. How to query the database using an energy range

```

899 The syntax is : $histoGe -q minVal maxVal
900 $ histoGe -q 300 300.1

901 The energy range consulted is 300.00 keV to 300.10 keV.
902
903 Eg (keV)  Ig (%)  Decay mode  Half life  Parent
904 300.0 3    0.015 4    a    2.78 h 17    224Ac
905 300.0 3    0.0225 15   b-    21.8 m 4     223Fr

```

```

906 300.0 1 0.15 3 b- 9.1 m 1 236Pa
907 300.0 16 0.23 4 e+b+ 17.9 m 3 151Dy
908 300.0 3 0.34 5 a 18.72 d 2 227Th
909 300.0 3 2.32 17 a 18.72 d 2 227Th
910 300.0 5.2 5 e+b+ 21.2 s 4 179Pt
911 300.0 2 6.0 12 e+b+ 10.0 s 1 134Sm
912 300.0 4 12 1* e+b+ 59.0 s 2 116Xe
913 300.0 4 19 1* e+b+ 2.38 m 4 171W
914 300.0 3 0.015 4 a 2.78 h 17 224Ac
915 300.0 3 0.0225 15 b- 21.8 m 4 223Fr
916 300.0 1 0.15 3 b- 9.1 m 1 236Pa
917 300.0 16 0.23 4 e+b+ 17.9 m 3 151Dy
918 300.0 3 0.34 5 a 18.72 d 2 227Th
919 300.0 3 2.32 17 a 18.72 d 2 227Th
920 300.0 5.2 5 e+b+ 21.2 s 4 179Pt
921 300.0 2 6.0 12 e+b+ 10.0 s 1 134Sm
922 300.0 4 12 1* e+b+ 59.0 s 2 116Xe
923 300.0 4 19 1* e+b+ 2.38 m 4 171W
924 300.07 1 2.46 7 a 32760.0 y 110 231Pa
925 300.07 1 4.6 b- 42.2 m 5 227Ra
926 300.07 2 23.5 3 e+b+ 17.7 h 2 135Ce
927 300.087 10 3.28 3 b- 10.64 h 1 212Pb
928 300.1 7 0.44 4 e+b+ 27.0 m 1 199Bi

```

929 N. How to make a rank using the Ranking Criteria

930 The main structure of the command line is this:

```

931 $ histoGe filename.info filename.xxx --rankingCriteria rankingCriteriaSuboption --wof --all
932 in case the ranking criteria needs a sub option it must be typed next to the main option, if it doesn't specified the
933 criteria will use the default option. There are two different kinds of ways to rank the different peaks in a spectrum.
934 There are ranking criteria that only use an info file and ranking criteria that uses info file plus spectrum file.

```

935 The two optional arguments in the command line are to help the user to Write in an Output File and see All the
936 isotopes used in the criteria. The options are: `-wof --all`. Next shows an example of the syntax of each of ranking
937 criteria described in the manuscript:

938 Syntax for γ -line distance from peak mean:

```

939 $histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --probability
940

```

941 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

942	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank F	Probability	Distance	
943	0	1172.90	84.00	b-	9.00e+01 [s]	62Co	0.722	0.986650	0.019532
944	1	1172.90	0.34	e+b+	5.84e+02 [s]	62Cu	0.579	0.986650	0.019532
945	2	1172.90	98.00	b-	8.35e+02 [s]	62mCo	0.507	0.986650	0.019532
946	3	1172.90	0.71	e+b+	2.39e+02 [s]	158Tm	0.027	0.986650	0.019532
947	4	1172.90	1.09	b-	8.26e+03 [s]	132I	0.004	0.986650	0.019532
948	5	1172.90	0.05	e+b+	1.75e+04 [s]	85mY	0.001	0.986650	0.019532
949	6	1172.90	0.00	b-	2.71e+04 [s]	171Er	0.000	0.986650	0.019532
950	7	1172.87	2.50	b-	1.61e+02 [s]	116Ag	0.014	0.966155	0.049532
951	8	1172.98	0.05	b-	1.19e+03 [s]	214Bi	0.000	0.958688	0.060468
952	9	1173.00	3.50	e+b+	2.90e+01 [s]	124La	0.009	0.945043	0.080468

953 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

954	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank F	Probability	Distance	
955	0	1332.501	99.99	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	1.000	0.992057	0.015731
956	1	1332.501	88.00	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	0.442	0.992057	0.015731
957	2	1332.501	0.24	b-	6.28e+02 [s]	60mCo	0.107	0.992057	0.015731
958	3	1332.500	0.50	b-	4.45e+02 [s]	93Sr	0.006	0.991552	0.016731
959	4	1332.500	0.05	e+b+	7.56e+02 [s]	157Ho	0.004	0.991552	0.016731
960	5	1332.500	0.01	e+b+	1.05e+03 [s]	167Yb	0.000	0.991552	0.016731
961	6	1332.600	0.30	b-	3.80e+01 [s]	228Fr	0.025	0.957972	0.083269

```

965 7 1332.630 0.11 e+b+ 2.88e+03 [s] 155Ho 0.001 0.942853 0.113269
966 8 1332.400 0.01 b- 5.34e+00 [s] 96Y 0.016 0.941109 0.116731
967 9 1332.400 0.09 e+b+ 1.13e+04 [s] 173Ta 0.003 0.941109 0.116731

```

968 Syntax for γ -line coincidence probability:

```
969 $histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --distance
```

970

971 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

```
972
973      Eg [keV]  Ig (%) Decay mode      Half Life Parent  Rank F  Probability  Distance
974  0  1172.90  84.00      b-  9.00e+01 [s]  62Co  0.722  0.986650  0.019532
975  1  1172.90  0.34      e+b+ 5.84e+02 [s]  62Cu  0.579  0.986650  0.019532
976  2  1172.90  98.00      b-  8.35e+02 [s]  62mCo 0.507  0.986650  0.019532
977  3  1172.90  0.71      e+b+ 2.39e+02 [s]  158Tm 0.027  0.986650  0.019532
978  4  1172.90  1.09      b-  8.26e+03 [s]  132I  0.004  0.986650  0.019532
979  5  1172.90  0.05      e+b+ 1.75e+04 [s]  85mY  0.001  0.986650  0.019532
980  6  1172.90  0.00      b-  2.71e+04 [s]  171Er 0.000  0.986650  0.019532
981  7  1172.87  2.50      b-  1.61e+02 [s]  116Ag 0.014  0.966155  0.049532
982  8  1172.98  0.05      b-  1.19e+03 [s]  214Bi 0.000  0.958688  0.060468
983  9  1173.00  3.50      e+b+ 2.90e+01 [s]  124La 0.009  0.945043  0.080468

```

984

985 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

```
986
987      Eg [keV]  Ig (%) Decay mode      Half Life Parent  Rank F  Probability  Distance
988  0  1332.501  99.99      b-  1.66e+08 [s]  60Co  1.000  0.992057  0.015731
989  1  1332.501  88.00      e+b+ 1.42e+03 [s]  60Cu  0.442  0.992057  0.015731
990  2  1332.501  0.24      b-  6.28e+02 [s]  60mCo 0.107  0.992057  0.015731
991  3  1332.500  0.50      b-  4.45e+02 [s]  93Sr  0.006  0.991552  0.016731
992  4  1332.500  0.05      e+b+ 7.56e+02 [s]  157Ho 0.004  0.991552  0.016731
993  5  1332.500  0.01      e+b+ 1.05e+03 [s]  167Yb 0.000  0.991552  0.016731
994  6  1332.600  0.30      b-  3.80e+01 [s]  228Fr 0.025  0.957972  0.083269
995  7  1332.630  0.11      e+b+ 2.88e+03 [s]  155Ho 0.001  0.942853  0.113269
996  8  1332.400  0.01      b-  5.34e+00 [s]  96Y  0.016  0.941109  0.116731
997  9  1332.400  0.09      e+b+ 1.13e+04 [s]  173Ta 0.003  0.941109  0.116731

```

998 Syntax for Half-life sorting (isotope):

```
999 $histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --halfSort
```

1000

1001 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1002

```
1003      Eg [keV]  Ig (%) Decay m      Half Life Parent
1004  0  1170.93 (11)  0.04      e+b+ 4.27e+08 [s]  152Eu
1005  1  1171.24 (14)  0.00      b-  2.71e+08 [s]  154Eu
1006  2  1173.237 (4)  99.97      b-  1.66e+08 [s]  60Co
1007  3  1173.779 (10)  1.21      e+b+ 1.46e+06 [s]  184mRe
1008  4  1175.102 (6)  2.28      e+b+ 6.68e+05 [s]  56Co
1009  5  1176.0 (5)  0.00      b-  2.90e+05 [s]  129mTe
1010  6  1172.81 (12)  0.00      e+b+ 2.08e+05 [s]  147Eu
1011  7  1174.56 (4)  1.32      e+b+ 1.49e+05 [s]  188Ir
1012  8  1174.59 (10)  0.00      e+b+ 1.49e+05 [s]  188Ir
1013  9  1175.36 (4)  2.01      e+b+ 1.37e+05 [s]  194Au

```

1014

1015 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1016

```
1017      Eg [keV]  Ig (%) Decay m      Half Life Parent
1018  0  1331.24 (20)  0.00      b-  3.78e+10 [s]  166mHo
1019  1  1334.06 (25)  0.41      e+b+ 1.16e+09 [s]  150Eu
1020  2  1332.501 (5)  99.99      b-  1.66e+08 [s]  60Co
1021  3  1334.34 (20)  0.14      b-  2.16e+06 [s]  110mAg
1022  4  1331.324 (15)  0.00      e+b+ 8.04e+05 [s]  168Tm
1023  5  1335.589 (8)  0.12      e+b+ 6.68e+05 [s]  56Co
1024  6  1331.526 (23)  0.08      e+b+ 2.35e+05 [s]  71As
1025  7  1330.962 (20)  0.38      e+b+ 2.30e+05 [s]  182Re

```

1026 8 1331.997 (13) 0.33 e+b+ 2.08e+05 [s] 147Eu
 1027 9 1331.95 (4) 0.47 e+b+ 1.49e+05 [s] 188Ir

1028 Syntax for Peak Explanation Power:

1029 \$histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --rank D

1030

1031 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1032

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank D	Rank E	Rank F	
1033	0	1175.09	0.14	e+b+	3.98e+04 [s]	146Eu	6	0.040	0.002
1034	1	1172.53	0.11	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	6	0.036	0.002
1035	2	1174.90	0.04	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	6	0.036	0.002
1036	3	1174.56	1.32	e+b+	1.49e+05 [s]	188Ir	5	0.085	0.014
1037	4	1174.59	0.00	e+b+	1.49e+05 [s]	188Ir	5	0.085	0.014
1038	5	1171.94	10.00	e+b+	4.56e+02 [s]	189Hg	5	0.046	0.007
1039	6	1174.20	1.29	b-	3.80e+01 [s]	228Fr	4	0.059	0.025
1040	7	1171.00	0.40	b-	3.80e+01 [s]	228Fr	4	0.059	0.025
1041	8	1174.00	2.10	e+b+	4.25e+04 [s]	193mHg	4	0.036	0.017
1042	9	1171.50	1.20	e+b+	4.25e+04 [s]	193mHg	4	0.036	0.017

1044

1045 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1046

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank D	Rank E	Rank F	
1047	0	1332.74	0.19	e+b+	3.98e+04 [s]	146Eu	6	0.040	0.002
1048	1	1335.52	0.13	e+b+	3.98e+04 [s]	146Eu	6	0.040	0.002
1049	2	1336.01	0.04	e+b+	3.98e+04 [s]	146Eu	6	0.040	0.002
1050	3	1330.33	0.03	e+b+	3.98e+04 [s]	146Eu	6	0.040	0.002
1051	4	1333.10	0.10	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	6	0.036	0.002
1052	5	1329.50	0.05	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	6	0.036	0.002
1053	6	1332.30	0.01	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	6	0.036	0.002
1054	7	1331.95	0.47	e+b+	1.49e+05 [s]	188Ir	5	0.085	0.014
1055	8	1336.38	0.14	e+b+	1.49e+05 [s]	188Ir	5	0.085	0.014
1056	9	1331.30	2.60	e+b+	4.56e+02 [s]	189Hg	5	0.046	0.007

1058 Syntax for Improve Peak Explanation Power:

1059 \$histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --rank E

1060

1061 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1062

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank D	Rank E	Rank F	
1063	0	1173.237	99.97	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.000	1.000
1064	1	1171.300	1.70	e+b+	9.53e+02 [s]	120Sb	1	1.000	0.889
1065	2	1171.300	100.00	e+b+	4.98e+04 [s]	120mSb	1	1.000	0.273
1066	3	1171.300	100.00	b-	4.73e+01 [s]	120m2In	1	1.000	0.210
1067	4	1174.000	11.00	e+b+	8.90e+00 [s]	76Sr	1	1.000	0.077
1068	5	1172.400	8.00	b-	3.40e-01 [s]	128Cd	1	1.000	0.040
1069	6	1175.600	1.00	e+b+	9.50e+00 [s]	82Y	1	1.000	0.026
1070	7	1171.000	0.00	b-	1.13e+04 [s]	232Pa	1	1.000	0.000
1071	8	1173.890	0.00	e+b+	7.02e+04 [s]	135La	1	1.000	0.000
1072	9	1171.500	2.10	b-	5.45e-01 [s]	80Zn	2	0.667	0.033

1074

1075 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1076

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank D	Rank E	Rank F	
1077	0	1332.501	99.99	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.000	1.000
1078	1	1331.100	130.00	e+b+	3.00e+02 [s]	178Os	1	1.000	0.167
1079	2	1332.501	0.24	b-	6.28e+02 [s]	60mCo	1	1.000	0.107
1080	3	1330.000	9.50	b-	3.20e-01 [s]	120mAg	1	1.000	0.043
1081	4	1330.300	0.28	e+b+	9.00e+01 [s]	180Ir	1	1.000	0.002
1082	5	1334.090	5.60	b-	5.45e-01 [s]	80Zn	2	0.667	0.033
1083	6	1330.000	4.50	b-	1.23e+00 [s]	120Ag	1	0.500	0.036
1084	7	1333.120	0.00	b-	3.07e+02 [s]	66Cu	1	0.500	0.000
1085	8	1334.960	0.05	b-	3.13e+04 [s]	184Ta	3	0.375	0.016
1086	9	1335.040	71.00	b-	2.36e+00 [s]	125In	1	0.333	0.693

1088 Syntax for Relative Emission Probability

1089 \$hismoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --rank F

1090

1091 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1092

1093	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank D	Rank E	Rank F	
1094	0	1173.237	99.97	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.000	1.000
1095	1	1171.300	1.70	e+b+	9.53e+02 [s]	120Sb	1	1.000	0.889
1096	2	1171.300	19.00	b-	3.08e+00 [s]	120In	1	0.167	0.731
1097	3	1172.900	84.00	b-	9.00e+01 [s]	62Co	1	0.200	0.722
1098	4	1172.900	0.34	e+b+	5.84e+02 [s]	62Cu	1	0.200	0.579
1099	5	1172.900	98.00	b-	8.35e+02 [s]	62mCo	2	0.400	0.507
1100	6	1173.237	0.26	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	2	0.091	0.442
1101	7	1171.300	96.00	b-	4.62e+00 [s]	120mIn	1	0.111	0.389
1102	8	1171.300	100.00	e+b+	4.98e+04 [s]	120mSb	1	1.000	0.273
1103	9	1176.100	66.30	e+b+	9.20e+00 [s]	98Cd	1	0.167	0.239

1104

1105 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1106

1107	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank D	Rank E	Rank F	
1108	0	1332.501	99.99	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.000	1.000
1109	1	1335.040	71.00	b-	2.36e+00 [s]	125In	1	0.333	0.693
1110	2	1332.501	88.00	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	2	0.091	0.442
1111	3	1331.100	130.00	e+b+	3.00e+02 [s]	1780s	1	1.000	0.167
1112	4	1332.501	0.24	b-	6.28e+02 [s]	60mCo	1	1.000	0.107
1113	5	1331.810	7.00	e+b+	5.04e+02 [s]	187Au	3	0.033	0.078
1114	6	1331.200	2.90	e+b+	4.62e+02 [s]	102mAg	2	0.167	0.066
1115	7	1333.210	10.67	b-	7.50e+02 [s]	133Te	3	0.043	0.065
1116	8	1333.700	0.08	b-	7.50e+02 [s]	133Te	3	0.043	0.065
1117	9	1333.400	0.52	b-	1.70e+00 [s]	142Cs	2	0.095	0.059

1118 Syntax for Relative Emission Probability with Gilmore's statistics

1119 \$hismoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --rankAdv

1120

1121 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1122

1123	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank G	
1124	0	1173.237	99.97	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	0.055466
1125	1	1175.900	1.60	e+b+	5.00e+01 [s]	152mHo	0.141205
1126	2	1172.900	98.00	b-	8.35e+02 [s]	62mCo	0.151371
1127	3	1175.400	1.11	b-	4.58e+03 [s]	87Kr	0.222990
1128	4	1171.500	2.10	b-	5.45e-01 [s]	80Zn	0.257665
1129	5	1173.000	0.70	e+b+	1.57e+04 [s]	244Bk	0.304332
1130	6	1173.800	0.13	e+b+	2.68e+03 [s]	202Po	0.372907
1131	7	1172.530	0.11	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	0.444468
1132	8	1174.900	0.04	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	0.444468
1133	9	1171.700	0.13	b-	4.90e+01 [s]	226Fr	0.550328

1134

1135 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1136

1137	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay mode	Half Life	Parent	Rank G	
1138	0	1332.501	99.99	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	0.055466
1139	1	1331.700	1.70	e+b+	5.00e+01 [s]	152mHo	0.141205
1140	2	1333.210	10.67	b-	7.50e+02 [s]	133Te	0.161746
1141	3	1333.700	0.08	b-	7.50e+02 [s]	133Te	0.161746
1142	4	1334.090	5.60	b-	5.45e-01 [s]	80Zn	0.257665
1143	5	1333.000	1.20	e+b+	1.57e+04 [s]	244Bk	0.304332
1144	6	1335.000	0.21	e+b+	2.68e+03 [s]	202Po	0.372907
1145	7	1333.100	0.10	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	0.444468
1146	8	1329.500	0.05	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	0.444468
1147	9	1332.300	0.01	b-	7.46e+02 [s]	151Nd	0.444468

1148 Syntax for Fuzzy logic

1149 \$histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --fuzzy

1150

1151 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1152

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay m	Half Life	Parent	Adj MSE	Rank H
1153	0	1173.237	99.97	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	0.055466 0.999999
1154	1	1171.300	1.70	e+b+	9.53e+02 [s]	120Sb	1.000000 0.868809
1155	2	1171.300	19.00	b-	3.08e+00 [s]	120In	6.000000 0.601080
1156	3	1172.900	84.00	b-	9.00e+01 [s]	62Co	5.000000 0.590863
1157	4	1172.900	98.00	b-	8.35e+02 [s]	62mCo	0.151371 0.589085
1158	5	1171.500	2.10	b-	5.45e-01 [s]	80Zn	0.257665 0.466053
1159	6	1171.300	100.00	e+b+	4.98e+04 [s]	120mSb	1.000000 0.427518
1160	7	1173.237	0.26	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	4.857141 0.420260
1161	8	1171.300	100.00	b-	4.73e+01 [s]	120m2In	1.000000 0.400792
1162	9	1174.000	11.00	e+b+	8.90e+00 [s]	76Sr	1.000000 0.382981

1163

1164 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1165

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay m	Half Life	Parent	Adj MSE	Rank H
1166	0	1332.501	99.99	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	0.055466 0.999999
1167	1	1335.040	71.00	b-	2.36e+00 [s]	125In	3.000000 0.561852
1168	2	1334.090	5.60	b-	5.45e-01 [s]	80Zn	0.257665 0.466053
1169	3	1332.501	88.00	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	4.857141 0.420260
1170	4	1331.100	130.00	e+b+	3.00e+02 [s]	1780s	1.000000 0.390529
1171	5	1332.501	0.24	b-	6.28e+02 [s]	60mCo	1.000000 0.384215
1172	6	1330.000	9.50	b-	3.20e-01 [s]	120mAg	1.000000 0.382320
1173	7	1330.300	0.28	e+b+	9.00e+01 [s]	180Ir	1.000000 0.382045
1174	8	1331.700	1.70	e+b+	5.00e+01 [s]	152mHo	0.141205 0.263417
1175	9	1333.210	10.67	b-	7.50e+02 [s]	133Te	0.161746 0.262098

1176

1177 Syntax for Decay chain Peak members

1178

1179 \$histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --chainRank

1180

1181 The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1182

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay m	Half Life	Parent	Rank C	Rank D	Rank E	Rank I	Rank J
1183	0	1173.237	99.97000	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.00000	1.00000	0.50000 0.49996
1184	1	1172.9	0.34000	e+b+	5.84e+02 [s]	62Cu	1	0.20000	0.57900	0.10000 0.28972
1185	2	1172.9	84.00000	b-	9.00e+01 [s]	62Co	1	0.20000	0.72200	0.06667 0.24069
1186	3	1173.237	0.26000	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	2	0.09100	0.44200	0.04545 0.22078
1187	4	1172.3	1.60000	b-	6.50e-01 [s]	125Cd	1	0.04200	0.00900	0.10938 0.17697
1188	5	1173.3	0.18000	b-	8.33e+04 [s]	125Sn	1	0.06200	0.00500	0.10938 0.17697
1189	6	1174.0	11.00000	e+b+	8.90e+00 [s]	76Sr	1	1.00000	0.07700	0.30500 0.02584
1190	7	1174.0	2.72000	e+b+	3.65e+01 [s]	76Rb	3	0.20000	0.02600	0.30500 0.02584
1191	8	1172.4	8.00000	b-	3.40e-01 [s]	128Cd	1	1.00000	0.04000	0.26250 0.02096
1192	9	1173.18	0.88000	e+b+	5.30e+02 [s]	143Sm	1	0.07700	0.10100	0.01538 0.02020

1193

1194 The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1195

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay m	Half Life	Parent	Rank C	Rank D	Rank E	Rank I	Rank J
1196	0	1332.501	99.99000	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.00000	1.00000	0.50000 0.49996
1197	1	1332.501	88.00000	e+b+	1.42e+03 [s]	60Cu	2	0.09100	0.44200	0.04545 0.22078
1198	2	1335.04	71.00000	b-	2.36e+00 [s]	125In	1	0.33300	0.69300	0.10938 0.17697
1199	3	1334.4	0.37000	e+b+	3.65e+01 [s]	76Rb	3	0.20000	0.02600	0.30500 0.02584
1200	4	1331.8	2.50000	e+b+	8.16e+01 [s]	101Cd	1	0.02400	0.01400	0.01926 0.01985
1201	5	1330.0	4.50000	b-	1.23e+00 [s]	120Ag	1	0.50000	0.03600	0.25000 0.01793
1202	6	1333.4	0.52000	b-	1.70e+00 [s]	142Cs	2	0.09500	0.05900	0.02844 0.01622
1203	7	1329.61	7.00000	b-	1.85e+00 [s]	83Ge	1	0.07700	0.02000	0.04423 0.01598
1204	8	1331.0	6.80000	b-	1.34e+01 [s]	83As	1	0.10000	0.04400	0.04423 0.01598
1205	9	1331.44	6.50000	b-	2.10e+00 [s]	123Cd	2	0.08000	0.05300	0.02000 0.01330

1206

1207 Syntax for Decay chain improved

1208

1209 \$histoGe co60_190828_cal.mca.info co60_190828_cal.mca --chainRank --peak

1210

The energy range consulted is between 1170.84 keV and 1176.18 keV.

1212

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay m	Half Life	Parent	Rank C	Rank D	Rank E	Rank I	Rank J
1214	0	1173.237	99.97000	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.00000	1.00000	0.50000 0.49996
1215	1	1175.6	1.00000	e+b+	9.50e+00 [s]	82Y	1	1.00000	0.02600	0.50000 0.01305
1216	2	1174.0	11.00000	e+b+	8.90e+00 [s]	76Sr	1	1.00000	0.07700	0.30500 0.02584
1217	3	1174.0	2.72000	e+b+	3.65e+01 [s]	76Rb	3	0.20000	0.02600	0.30500 0.02584
1218	4	1172.4	8.00000	b-	3.40e-01 [s]	128Cd	1	1.00000	0.04000	0.26250 0.02096
1219	5	1172.1	1.10000	e+b+	7.44e+02 [s]	135Nd	1	0.25000	0.00600	0.20049 0.00164
1220	6	1173.92	0.18000	e+b+	6.37e+04 [s]	135Ce	3	0.10300	0.00200	0.20049 0.00164
1221	7	1173.92	0.18000	e+b+	6.37e+04 [s]	135Ce	3	0.10300	0.00200	0.20049 0.00164
1222	8	1173.89	0.00000	e+b+	7.02e+04 [s]	135La	1	1.00000	0.00000	0.20049 0.00164
1223	9	1175.04	0.04000	b-	5.34e+00 [s]	96Y	3	0.23100	0.01600	0.19784 0.01106

1224

The energy range consulted is between 1329.41 keV and 1336.54 keV.

1226

	Eg [keV]	Ig (%)	Decay m	Half Life	Parent	Rank C	Rank D	Rank E	Rank I	Rank J
1227	0	1332.501	99.99000	b-	1.66e+08 [s]	60Co	2	1.00000	1.00000	0.50000 0.49996
1228	1	1330.3	0.28000	e+b+	9.00e+01 [s]	180Ir	1	1.00000	0.00200	0.34058 0.00065
1229	2	1333.384	0.05000	e+b+	1.46e+02 [s]	180Re	1	0.02200	0.00000	0.34058 0.00065
1230	3	1334.4	0.37000	e+b+	3.65e+01 [s]	76Rb	3	0.20000	0.02600	0.30500 0.02584
1231	4	1330.0	4.50000	b-	1.23e+00 [s]	120Ag	1	0.50000	0.03600	0.25000 0.01793
1232	5	1334.7	0.04000	e+b+	6.37e+04 [s]	135Ce	3	0.10300	0.00200	0.20049 0.00164
1233	6	1335.9	2.53000	b-	1.99e-01 [s]	96Rb	1	0.02900	0.01400	0.19784 0.01106
1234	7	1331.6	0.61000	b-	1.07e+00 [s]	96Sr	1	0.33300	0.00300	0.19784 0.01106
1235	8	1332.4	0.01000	b-	5.34e+00 [s]	96Y	3	0.23100	0.01600	0.19784 0.01106
1236	9	1334.96	0.05000	b-	3.13e+04 [s]	184Ta	3	0.37500	0.01600	0.12500 0.00520

1238

O. How to generate info files for Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM)

1239 `histoGe` can generate an `info` file with the most significant peaks/ γ -lines of a NORM included in the table 16.1 of
 1240 Gilmore's book [1]. The user can use the option `--NORM` with the name of one or multiple isotopes and `histoGe` will
 1241 save an `info` in the current path where the instruction was executed. The available series are 235U, 238U, 232Th,
 1242 40K, and 7Be. The structure of the command is this:

1243 `$ histoGe --NORM --isotope_1 --isotope_2 --isotope_N range`

1244 where `range` is an optional argument (default = 1 keV) that specifies the size of the interval that contains the peaks
 1245 of interest. The syntax for Uranium 235, Thorium 232, Potassium 40 and their outputs look like these:

```

1246 $ histoGe --NORM --235U
1247         start      end
1248 235U_1  142.764  144.764
1249 235U_2  162.358  164.358
1250 235U_3  184.712  186.712
1251 235U_4  204.309  206.309
1252 227Th_1 234.971  236.971
1253 227Th_2 255.25  257.25
1254 223Ra   268.459  270.459
1255 219Rn_1 270.23  272.23
1256 219Rn_2 400.81  402.81
1257
1258 $ histoGe --NORM --232Th --40K
1259
1260         start      end
1261 232Th   62.83  64.83
1262 212Pb_1 237.632  239.632
1263 212Pb_2 299.087  301.087
1264 228Ac_3 337.32  339.32
1265 208Tl_4 509.77  511.77
1266 208Tl_2 582.191  584.191
1267 212Bi_1 726.33  728.33
1268 208Tl_3 859.564  861.564

```

1269	228Ac_1	910.204	912.204
1270	228Ac_4	963.766	965.766
1271	228Ac_2	967.971	969.971
1272	212Bi_1	1619.5	1621.5
1273	208Tl_1	2613.533	2615.533
1274			
1275		start	end
1276	40K	1459.83	1461.83

1277

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